

Structural-semantic analysis of phraseological units in English and Uzbek

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Abstract

In this article, the scientific and structural-semantic aspects of phraseological units in linguistics are highlighted and researches conducted in the field of linguistics are discussed.

Keyword: linguistics, phraseology, phraseologisms, word combinations, communication, structural-semantics.

INTRODUCTION

Phraseological units used in the language occur not only with the emergence of phrasemic new words, but also on the basis of semantic, grammatical and functional updating of existing phrases. He rightly said that it is wrong to understand a phrase as an invariable unit of language. Rakhmatullayev points out that the wider the nature of the words that merge into the phrase, the more changes in the composition of the phrase can occur. These changes are referred to as the phraseologisms transformations.. In her monograph, Barno Boltaeva argues that the structural transformation of phraseologisms in linguistics, the transformational system in general, has not found its solution both on a general scale and in the occasional plan by this time. This is, firstly, the fact that both phraseologisms in general and phraseologisms in the language of some derived word masters are not created, covering cases of change, and secondly, most theoretical issues of transformation are not well-founded and correctly solved, or there are different views about it.

Phraseologisms also exist, like a word, as a dialectical unit of form and content. The form of a phraseology is its exterior, appearance, and is the basis of the plan of expression, component composition, structural construction or material. And the content of the phraseology is its internal structure or semantics. For example, if we analyze according to the classification, while the phraseology “ishlar xurjun” expresses the meaning of “the work is not going well”, its form - form of expression is a convoluted simple sentence with two contents. N. Yakubov, in his “In search of water“, instead expanded the work from context: “Zavodda suv masalasi xurjun: texnologiya talablari yaxshi bajarilmayotir.”

As mentioned above, in the structure of a phraseological unit, component changes also affect its semantics. For example, in the literary language there is an expression for drawing the Earth, which is used to mean to suck, to fantasize. Askad Muxtor was able to reinforce its meaning by adding a word in his novel: “Bozorqul keragaga suyanib o‘tirgancha yer chizib qoldiz”. In colloquial style, however, the phrase “yer chizmoq” was embarrassed, also used in the sense of shame.

Phraseologisms can be structurally modified depending on the user's expression of opinion, even if they are seen as brought in ready-to-talk, depending on his or her skill. It is worth mentioning at this point that when analyzing phraseological units semantically-structurally, it is necessary to

distinguish their connotative meaning. Yuldashev expresses his opinion and expresses his objection that in the course of studying Rakhmatullayev and other phraseological and synonym dictionaries, the methodological meanings of phrasemes are not given, noting that the explanation of phrasemes to perish is given as the same perish. In fact, semantically perish should be used in relation to newborns, and perish should be used in relation to people who have died of old age. To give a more complete understanding, let's give examples of the meanings of the verb To Die. *Yana ko 'zini yumdi, shu yumgancha qaytib ochmadi-saharga borib uzildi.* (A.Kahhor. Patient) in this statement, the word interrupted is being used to refer to a patient lying on his deathbed. The Dakhshat story also uses the same phrase for Unsin: *Biroq Unsin peshungacha yetmadi-uzildi.* (A.Kahhor. Dakhshat) the word disconnected is actually a reduced form of the phrase disconnected from the soul, even if it does not resemble a phrase from the structure. In fiction, writers transform phrases by changing them in different ways.

We can also analyze the semantic properties of phraseologisms and see that they have been found to contain phraseological polysemy, phraseological synonymy, phraseological antonymy, and paronymy phenomena. One of the Uzbek phraseologists, Sh.Rahmatullayev also explained the semantic and grammatical nature of phrases in his book "Phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language". Paradigmatic and syntagmatic features of phraseologisms indicate the use of grammatical, morphological, syntactic and lexical-semantic tools in them.

Phraseologisms-the exchange, application, descent of their components-depend on transformation. On the basis of the replacement of its components by one word or another, phraseologisms with a close meaning are formed. In this, basically, the form changes, while the meaning practically does not change. Phraseologisms formed on the basis of lexical and structural-grammatical modifications are called phraseological variation and phraseological synonymy in linguistics. On the basis of the replacement of its components by one word or another, phraseologisms with a close meaning are formed. In this, basically, the form changes, while the meaning practically does not change. But the phenomena of phraseological variation and phraseological synonymy should be clearly distinguished from each other. Phraseological synonymy refers to phraseologisms with different structures that represent one meaning. In this, each synonym phraseologism is formed in different images, and they do not even have a common word - component. Synonymous phraseologisms arise not on the basis of universal phraseologisms, but on the basis of a system of linguistic phraseological formation, in different circles, under the influence of linguistic and non-linguistic factors. Phraseological variants, on the other hand, arise on the basis of universal phraseologisms, and are either based on certain phraseologisms, or have evolved from phraseologisms present in the language. Phraseological variation is part of the formation system of new phraseologisms on the basis of general phraseologisms³⁸. So, to explain more simply, if all of the components of a phraseology are replaced by a meaningless word it will be synonymous, or it will be option if there is only one word or morphemic change in the composition of the phrase. For example, to give up - to go through Bahri, to put the sentence in one place - to collide, to load it on the Gardani - to put it on the neck, the dami did not come out - to bite the wax, the beak was choked - to be disappointed, to hold the collar - to be surprised-these are exchanging all components with the meaning saved, and phraseological synonymy is going on. The head has reached the sky - the head has reached the sky, the joy does not fit into it - the joy does not fit into the body, the heart has risen like a mountain-and in these phraseologisms, an alternative is formed through a single component change. It seems that in this the variety of images and lexical content distinguishes them from each other. English is also rich in Lexic-semantic synonyms. For example, below we found nine synonyms for the word happy -happy, and there may be already more synonyms that we do not know. That

being said, when using phrasemes, it is necessary to pay attention to their exact meaning, since, depending on the context, what kind of work –activity it is used, its meanings differ to some extent.

Be on top of the world Boshi ko 'kga yetmoq

Be in seventh heaven Yettinchi osmonda uchmoq

Be like a kid with a new toy Yosh boladek quvonmoq

Thank one's lucky stars Ko 'ngli chog' bo'lmoq

Walk on air Havoda uchmoq

Look like the cat that swallowed the canary, Yelkasidan tog' qulagandek bo'lmoq

Be on cloud nine Bulutlarda yurmoq

Be thrilled to death Quvonchdan terisiga sig'maslik

Be happy as Lary Og'zi qulogida bo'lmoq

Be happy as a pig in shit Itdek yayramoq

“Bu yilning planlarini bajarsak ham do'ppimizni osmonga otardik.” (Sh.Rashidov, Bo'rondan kuchli.)

“I am sure you are walking on air,” my mother said to Paul at his wedding. (Bernard MacLaverty. Secrets)

The consonants associated with the word Happy are varied consonants, and a certain number rank the word happy. In the following examples, the word happy itself serves as a rank: happy bunny, happy camper, happy chance, happy dance, happy event, happy birthday. These are shameful words, According to Sh. Rakhmatullayev, the amount of phrases that combine into one synonymy slot is different: there are also slots that combine two, three or four phrases, which differ depending on how little is used in speech.

In conclusion, a number of works have been carried out in English and Uzbek linguistics on the semantic-structural structure of phraseological units.

Phraseological units are semantically-structurally expanded or reduced in composition by transformation, and figurativeness is achieved. Among them, the phenomenon of synonymy, homogeneity, antonyms and polysemanticity is observed in the same way as in words.

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